

A Phenomenological Inquiry into Radiologic Technology Interns for Their Performance in Public and Private Hospital Environments

¹Alexandra Mae B. Bonifacio, ²Angelica Mae A. Magboo, ³Elizabeth Ashley L. Pampuan,
⁴Irish Mae A. Prado, ⁵Edward Dale Roranes

Calamba Doctors' College

¹ambonifacio@calambadoctorscollege.edu.ph, ²ammagboo@calambadoctorscollege.edu.ph,

³epampuan@calambadoctorscollege.edu.ph, ⁴iprado@calambadoctorscollege.edu.ph,

⁵edward@calambadoctorscollege.edu.ph

Article Details:

Received: 22 April 2026

Revised: 1 May 2026

Accepted: 9 May 2026

Published: 31 May 2026

Corresponding Email:

ambonifacio@calambadoctorscollege.edu.ph

Recommended Citation:

Bonifacio A. M. B., Magboo, A. M. A., Pampuan, E. A. L., Prado, I. M. A., Roranes, E. D. (2026) A Phenomenological Inquiry into Radiologic Technology Interns for Their Performance in Public and Private Hospital Environments. The International Review of Multidisciplinary Research. 1 (7), 21-33.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20479490>

Index Terms:

radiologic technology interns, public hospitals, private hospitals, clinical internship, clinical performance, workload, supervision, learning opportunities

Abstract. Radiologic technology interns encounter varied clinical environments that may significantly influence their performance, yet empirical evidence on differences between public and private hospital settings remains limited. This study aimed to explore how variations in clinical training environments across hospital settings shape intern learning outcomes, skill development and professional growth. A phenomenological research design with transcendental phenomenological data analysis was utilized. Purposive sampling was used to select 6 senior radiologic technology interns from Calamba Doctors' College, with 3 participants from public hospitals and 3 from private hospitals. The following criteria were applied: (1) interns currently deployed in their clinical internship sites; (2) interns with at least three months of clinical exposure; and (3) interns willing to share their lived experiences. The study revealed that radiologic technology interns gain diverse and valuable experiences in both public and private hospitals, particularly concerning workload, supervision, learning opportunities, and the challenges they encounter. Public hospitals were characterized by higher patient volumes, which, in most cases, resulted in physically demanding and sometimes toxic work environments. Yet, the heavy workload enabled the interns to have a lot of hands-on experience, especially dealing with trauma and other complex cases. Conversely, the workload in private hospitals was lighter because of fewer patients and a quicker workflow, which made the work environment less stressful and provided more exposure to advanced imaging modalities, but offered fewer opportunities due to stricter supervision.

Introduction

Clinical learning is essential as a foundation to undergraduate health professions that provide with the population to grow their skills, build confidence, adapt to the complexities in healthcare and effectively apply knowledge in real clinical settings. Over the last few years, the demand for medical imaging has been growing rapidly due to technological advancements, which have also led to higher demand for diagnostic services, patient demand, workload, and costs. Therefore, technological modernization can increase pressure on hospitals today. Such alterations demonstrate the importance of clinical training, where interns must not simply perform their duties because they are required, but also be aware of and mindful of how to adapt, adjust, and improve their communication skills and critical thinking. A study by Aguilar et al. (2023) showed that some respondents experienced issues during their clinical internships, particularly the lack of imaging resources and medical equipment, lack of mental support and feedback on the clinical performance of the interns, and insufficiency in the intern holding area. This indicates that hospital conditions could significantly affect the performance and experiences of interns as these environments influence their learning and skill development. Performance is a significant factor that influences behavior, learning, development of skills and quality of care that interns offer. The knowledge of what affects them in their performance directly affects their career growth and readiness to work in the healthcare field in the future. However, there is limited research on the investigation of the performance of the interns, specifically, the hospital environment whether public or private that influences the

performance of the intern and their future career choices. This study explores the performance of Radiologic Technology Senior interns during their internship and aims to provide insight and beneficial information to educators, institutions and clinical supervisors to make sure that interns are well-equipped and dedicated not only to technical skills but on adaptability and professionalism despite the clinical placement.

Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions:

Central Question

1. What is the essence of the experiences of Radiologic Technology interns regarding their performance in public and private hospital environments?

Corollary Question

1. How do Radiologic Technology interns describe their performance during internships between public and private hospitals?
2. What themes arise from the shared experiences of the participants?

Conceptual Framework

This Conceptual framework demonstrated how this study was processed. It served as a guide in the collection, analysis, and interpretation of data in the study. In particular, the use of triangulation methods, which guaranteed the validity and credibility of the findings, is depicted in the framework. It is a phenomenological study that focuses on the performance of the Radiologic Technology Senior Interns in Calamba Doctors' College in both public and private hospital settings.

As illustrated in Figure 1. It illustrates the process of gathering and treating data shown in the triangulation method.

Figure 1. Triangulation Method

At the centre of the framework is the phenomenological inquiry into radiologic technology interns for their performance in public and private hospital environments, and around it consists of three primary processes, namely Epoché, Phenomenological Reduction, and Imaginative Variation. In descriptive phenomenology, epoché is the bracketing procedure in which researchers attempt to explicitly put aside or hold back their past knowledge, hypotheses, or biases regarding the phenomena. At the same time, they listen to participants and examine the data (Willis et al., 2016, as cited in Oluka, 2025). Redescribing and making sense out of the recounted experience is referred to as phenomenological reduction (Finally, 2008, as cited in Alhazmi and Kaufman, 2022). It entails the critical analysis of the statements of the participants and the elimination of a few of the non-essential statements.

Imaginative variation may be exploited by the phenomenological researchers as a means of analysis to examine the occurrence of a particular phenomenon in consciousness. It involves the creative manipulation of different features or angles of the experience to explore the incident in a large number of ways (Turley et al., 2016, as cited in Cudjoe, 2023). In this study, imaginative variation has been used by analyzing the performance of the interns in the public and private hospital setting from different perspectives to reveal the deeper meaning and circumstances in which the interns' performance is shaped.

These processes have three primary outputs, which are Experience of the Participants, Emerging Themes, and Essence of the Experiences. The study is mostly concerned with the experience of the participants. The essence of Experiences is a deeper understanding of the performance of the intern during their clinical internship. The shared ideas or patterns shared by the participants are referred to as the Emerging Themes.

This model shows the cycle of the phenomenological analysis wherein the data is analyzed continually until the essence or meaning of the study or the performance of the interns becomes understandable. This theoretical approach based on the triangulation method is an advantage of the study as it annexes to the phenomenological processes Epoché (Oluka, 2025), phenomenological reduction (Alhazmi and Kauffman, 2022), and imaginative variation (Cudjoe, 2023).

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed transcendental phenomenology to explore Radiologic Technology interns' performance in public and private hospital environments. It focuses on studying people's lived experiences through their personal experiences. This approach is appropriate for uncovering their opinions, feelings, and experiences, which are crucial to their professional development. The researchers' biases will not be included through bracketing. This allowed for a more accurate understanding of the participants' personal experiences.

Participants and Sampling Technique

The participants of this study are composed of six (6) Radiologic Technology Senior Interns who are currently enrolled in Calamba Doctors' College.

Purposive Sampling (non-probability sampling method) was used to gather data on the respondents who have sufficient exposure. The purposive sampling technique is used in this study to help the researcher select participants who perceive and experience the phenomenon related to the study's objectives.

The criteria were:

1. Interns who are currently deployed in their respective clinical internship sites.
2. Interns should have at least three (3) months of clinical exposure in their respective hospital environment to ensure they have encountered sufficient experiences
3. Interns must be willing to engage and share their lived experiences.

Instrumentation

The study used semi-structured interviews, allowing researchers to give follow-up questions to further explore their experiences. The in-depth interview questions were well structured to have flow continuity to ensure the respondents could respond with clear, comprehensive, and reflective accounts of their lived experiences.

Validation of Instrument

The instrument employed was reviewed with the research advisers and also experts in the field of research and education to have content validation. It is based on their feedback and ideas to make the statements' structure better and make them relevant to the target participants. Complex structures of sentences have been redone in simpler and clearer sentences to achieve clarity and understanding. Unfamiliar terminology was corrected to make understanding simpler and clearer sentences have been adopted.

Data Gathering Procedure

The study was conducted by seeking the permission of the Calamba Doctors' College and the related hospitals where the majority of the interns are placed. The researchers then came up with a group of semi-structured interview questions that

will conform to the corollary and central questions of the study. The draft interview guides were then sent to the research adviser and field experts to ensure that they are validated. Recommendations and remarks were considered, and changes were made to ensure that the questions were succinct, pertinent, and fit the subjects, especially regarding their performance within the clinical environments.

Informed consent forms were given to the participants after the instruments were finalized. The researchers made sure that the purpose of the study, risks and benefits, voluntary participation, responses confidentiality and right to withdrawal are stated in the forms. Interviews were done when the respondents had free time and it did not interfere with their duties and personal lives. Interviews had been audio-taped or recorded with the consent of the participants and the researchers have made notes to record the key findings. Verbatim transcription of the audio recordings followed after data collection. The notes and transcripts were verified and prepared to be accurate and are now ready to undergo data analysis.

Data Analysis

The researchers transcribed the interview recordings verbatim after collecting all the data of the participants. The transcripts, as well as the field notes were repeatedly reviewed and arranged. Then, the researchers used transcendental phenomenology data analysis as per the procedures of Moustakas (1994), as referenced in Villanueva and Buenbrazo (2023). These steps included: (1) bracketing, (2) horizontalization, (3) clustering themes, (4) textual description, (5) structural description and (6) synthesis of text and structure.

The researchers started their research process by bracketing or epoché to get rid of the effect of preconceived notions, prior knowledge, and biases regarding the performance of the Radiologic Technology interns. This helped to keep the analysis fair and unbiased and ensured that it focused exclusively on the participants' responses. Specifically, only relying on the lived experiences as shared by the participants.

Horizontalization means collection of all the expressions that are verbatim and pertain to the study. All the answers were initially given equal value and irrelevant and repetitive statements were omitted. The researchers logically emphasized critical statements by offering an insight into the experiences of the interns. It was used to form the basis of the phenomenon under study through this process.

The clustering into themes was achieved through grouping the important statements to create broader themes. This enabled the researchers to narrow diverse experiences to consistent views that depict the performance of interns. The validity and accuracy of the themes were checked and met with field notes and observation data to review the themes.

The textural description was used to describe the experiences of the participants during their clinical internship as they were experienced and articulated. The themes were supported by the verbatim quotes of the interviews, giving the reflection of their performance during the internship clarity, authenticity, and validity.

To further expand the analysis, the structural descriptions have been furthered by looking at the way the interns' experience of performance evolved in the system of both the public and private hospitals. Through imaginative variation, the researchers took into consideration the various factors and conditions that may influence the performance of the participants in the course of clinical internship.

The researchers then generalized the findings to a textural-structural description. The textual description is the description of what the participants have undergone by providing a quote of what the respondents had actually said, whereas the structural description clarifies how the experiences occurred when they were training in the hospital. This defines the performance of radiologic technology interns as it is affected by their clinical internship experiences in both the public and private hospitals.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers conducted this study in accordance with established ethical guidelines that would ensure each participant's fairness, integrity, and respect. Prior to data collection, informed consent will be obtained so that each participant is aware of the study before agreeing to participate. Involvement will be entirely optional, and participants will be free to discontinue involvement at any time without any negative consequences. The researchers declare the principles of their honesty and accountability by making sure the information and the findings are genuine, no fabrication, modification, or forgery, thus protecting the credibility of the research and the credibility of the participants. Furthermore, participants' identities and responses will be protected in compliance with Republic Act No. 10173, also known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012, since the study's secrecy would be of utmost importance.

Reflexivity Statement

As a researcher and a future radiologic technology intern, our role in this study required careful reflection to maintain objectivity while exploring the experiences of Radiologic interns in a public and private hospital. We were mindful that our personal preferences regarding hospital exposure may impact how researchers interpreted the findings. Therefore, researchers intentionally set aside personal expectations or biases to guarantee that the participants' experiences were accurate and truly presented. Engaging with the reality of clinical practice helped us better to appreciate and understand the challenges that interns encounter, particularly in managing anxiety in a high-pressure healthcare setting, differences in modality exposure, strict supervision, and other more factors that contribute to their challenges and experiences. Moreover, this process of reflection reminded us of the significance of understanding, open-mindedness, and responsibility in qualitative research. It also helped us with our professional development, as we developed a better understanding of a radiologic technologist's responsibilities and the value of competence, accountability, and patient-centered care in clinical practice. Most significantly, this reflection deepened our understanding and awareness of how our perspectives as student interns may shape the way we interpret clinical experiences.

Results and Discussion

This qualitative study explored the experiences of the radiologic technology interns in the public and private hospitals. The study identified six key themes through in-depth interviews, highlighting factors, challenges, and learning processes in clinical internships. The themes highlighted that institutional environments, workload intensity, patient volume, resource availability, supervision, and procedural practices shape interns' learning experiences, skill development, and professional growth.

Theme 1. Registered Radiologic Technologists' Perceptions on the Role of Continuous Professional Development in Professional Growth

"Sa workload, sa isang araw mas marami kang puwedeng gamitin na modalities sa private kaysa sa public. Sa public naman, pasyente marami, as in per shift umaabot ng parang average 30 to 40 plus. Sa private naman, sa isang shift, parang marami na yung 20 ganoon, o kaya 25, knowing na mas mabilis mag-process sa private." (Amber)

"Yung sa pampubliko kasi, mas mabigat ang workload nila doon, CR palang yung gamit namin so pag na-toxic talaga, sobrang hirap tapos lalo ang dami nilang pasyente lagi sa public so ang tagal nung process unlike sa private na ambilis lang namin matapos yung position, pagka-scan lalabas agad sa computer." (Ruby)

"Sa workload mas maraming pasyente tayo sa public, tapos tatlo lang modalities. Tapos sa private naman, kakaunti ang pasyente, sobrang daming modalities." (Sapphire)

"Sa supervision, sa public, tinuruan din nila kami, pero nung nakita nilang okay na yung performance namin, hinahayaan na kami. Tapos sa private naman, maingat sila sa gamit kaya hindi nila masyadong pinapahawak sa amin kasi baka masira" (Sapphire)

"Sa supervision ng private mas strikto ang mga tech ng private kaysa sa public" (Garnet)

"Sa private hospital medyo mahigpit sa mga machines, tapos mahigpit din yung mga doctors at tapos yung mga bawal kang magkamali doon sa mga mga markers kasi sa public bawal din naman pero mas doon ko nafeel na mas magaan silang katrabaho kaysa sa mga nasa private." (Amethyst)

Participants emphasized that in private hospitals, the proper positioning and utilization of modalities are strictly followed, creating an accurate and accountable environment, which may create pressure. Technologists in public institutions are described as being more considerate. These findings correspond with the research conducted by O' Connor and McNulty (2024), which states that the quality of the clinical learning environment affects learners' experiences and development. It showed that the variations in clinical exposure, supervision, and professional expectations of the public and private hospitals can affect the learning outcomes of the intern, supporting the participant's observation of the stricter supervision in the private hospitals. This fact is affirmed by Irfan and Ijaz (2011) cited by Alumran (2020), who identified that the quality of care delivered in such aspects of healthcare as empathy, tangibles, assurance, timeliness, and responsiveness tends to be higher in private healthcare. This could indicate that stricter professional practices and supervision in private hospitals could help uphold standards of patient care and the quality of service delivery.

"Sa supervision, ay parehas lang. kahit magkaiba sila ng institution, ang tech iba-iba. Kami sa public may tech na maluwig, tech na mahigpit ganoon din sa private, may tech din na nagtatanong-tanong or nagpa-pop quiz, meron din naman sa public and private. Hindi siya ano eh, hindi mo siya mawe-weigh. Mawe-weigh in kung public or private. Parehas lang." (Amber)

However, this statement has brought out the variation in supervision based on the technologist's approach. The response suggests that supervision is the same, but it depends on the techs working with, rather than on the hospital type. Supporting this, Colina et al. (2023) compared the perceptions of a student toward clinical supervision in a Philippine-based school and discovered that approachable and supportive clinical supervisors had a strong influence on students' confidence and learning in clinical practice.

"Learning opportunities naman, syempre public, yung modalities bilang lang, mas marami akong mae-explore na modalities sa private. when it comes sa pagpapasyente, sa public, paulit-ulit lang yung views, kunwari, madalas sa chest, PA lang, AP, lateral ganyan. Tapos sa private mas marami yung views. Kunwari, shoulder AP with zanca view, ganoon o kaya sa knee APL, tapos may sunrise." (Amber)

"Sa public is ang daming pasyente so talagang matututo kayo pagdating sa positioning. Nakakapagod pero mahahasa kayo, unlike sa private. (Ruby)

In terms of learning opportunities, participants highlighted learning through procedural practice and exposure to broader modalities. Learning in private hospitals can take place through guided instruction and mentoring, whereas in public hospitals, learning is encouraged through repetition and extensive case exposure. A study by Tamayo et al. (2022) took place in a public hospital in Manila City, Philippines, which has the capacity to manage complex medical cases. The high numbers of patients can lead to repetition, and high case exposure will therefore assist in strengthening their abilities, confidence, and practical learning processes.

Theme 2: Institutional Differences in Clinical Challenges during Internship

Institutional variations in the public and private hospitals played a major role in the challenges that they encountered during the internship. The types of challenges interns faced and how they adapted to the clinical setting during their training were influenced by differences in workload demands, technological resources, and procedural expectations.

"Sa public, yung dagsa ng tao yung parang nakaka-pressure. Kasi minsan, may peak hours din talaga sa public eh pag patak mo ng 8am, yung mga nasa OPD, mga nagpapa-checkup eh. Sabihin natin, 30 to 50 doon need ng X-ray. Parang nakaka-pressure siya. Tapos syempre may mga bata at matanda mga ganon yun nga, sa workload din talaga doon talaga naikot lahat." (Amber)

"Sa public, ayon nga, sobrang daming pasyente at mga brutal yung mga pasyenteng na hahawakan namin. Tapos dito sa private, ang challenge diyan sa private ay kung paano ka makikisama sa mga kasama mong tech." (Sapphire)

"Sa private yung cases na na-handle ko dun parang pare-pareho lang mostly mga chest mas madali siya i posisyon, pero sa public since mga iba iba nga siya ng cases may mga Vehicular Accident may minsan may mga aksidente na malala talaga na bawal i-angat yung extremities nung pasyente. Mas na-cha-challenge ako sa public sa pagpo-posisyon ng pasyente kaysa sa private." (Emerald)

"Sa private super stricto doon pag dating ko sa public super luwag tapos doon na ako nanibago and then sa patients nanibago din ako doon kasi yun nga paulit ulit ako kasi yung patients sa private paisa isa lang yung bawat procedure sa isang patient pero kapag sa public sa isang patient madaming procedure ang gagawin sakanya." (Garnet)

Workload demands were emphasized by participants who mentioned that variations in patient volume and nature of tasks in the public hospitals gave them both challenges and opportunities to improve their technical competencies. According to the participants, a high workload associated with a complicated trauma case can affect the practical experience of the interns. In a study on Workload Indicators of Staffing Need (WISN), the researchers discovered that staffing levels in public healthcare facilities in Bangladesh are extremely high because of high volumes of patients and clients under the pressure of high workload, leading to the increased demands (Nuruzzaman, 2022).

"Sa pampubliko yung pangunahing hamon ay yung kakulangan sa mga gamit. So may mga chances na hindi natin magawa unlike sa private na halos kumpleto na sila." (Ruby)

"Sa private yung kumpleto kasi sila sa machines then ngayon yung nasa public na ko medyo nag a-adjust pa lang ako kasi CR yung gamit which is parang ang daming trabaho unlike yung digital na x-ray machine." (Amethyst)

These participants mentioned technological resources to be influential within the learning experiences of interns. The accessibility, completeness and up-to-date of imaging devices influenced the effectiveness and confidence of interns. The transitioning of CR systems in public hospitals to fully digital systems in private hospitals was also described, highlighting how technological differences influence the workflow and the acquisition of practical skills. In addition, constraints of equipment in the public hospitals were noted, which required a creative solution to complete procedures correctly. Chinene et al. (2023) analyzed the clinical experiences of radiography students in the public hospital and revealed that there were significant challenges, including the limited availability and poor condition of imaging equipment. Limitations to advanced imaging modalities such as MRI and gamma cameras were also observed as shortages in the study, and have therefore

limited the opportunities of students to utilize certain imaging procedures. These findings are further supported by Mishra (2024), who found that the advantage of private hospitals was mainly attributed to their perceived greater equipment and infrastructure compared with public hospitals.

“Sa standard, mas mataas kasi ang standard ng private so, alam natin na bawal basta basta magkamali so, mahigpit pagdating sa private lalo na sa mga patient, dapat maayos yung patient care mo.” (Ruby)

“Sa private super stricto doon pag dating ko sa public super luwag tapos doon na ako nanibago” (Garnet)

These participants found the presence of procedural expectations as the quality and strict protocols and standards tend to be more emphasized in private hospital settings compared to public ones. Participants described the need to carefully follow procedures, particularly when performing patient care or imaging tasks, which reinforced discipline and professional precision in clinical practice. In line with this observation, Begum et al. (2022) have shown that patients who were treated in private hospitals expressed higher levels of satisfaction, and this is because of the quality of services, the healthcare environment, and the responsiveness of healthcare providers.

Theme 3: Adaptive Coping Mechanisms during Clinical Internship

Various adaptive coping strategies were employed to deal with the pressure, stress, and challenges during their internships. These involve social support, self-directed learning habits and guidance from senior technologists, confidence and motivation, and perseverance. Such coping strategies indicate the active management of stress among interns, their ability to remain on track, and their motivation due to changes in workload, standards, and clinical environments.

“Coping mechanism siguro parehas ha, yung ano tulungan kami ng co-interns ko. Parang kapag may diskarte ako sa exposure, hindi nila ako pinapakialaman. Ganoon din, likewise, hindi ko rin sila pinapakialaman. Kung ganito yung strategy nila sa ganito, paano sila mag pasyente ng chest, paano kapag ang pasyente hindi makatayo, hinahayaan namin makadiskarte bawat isa. Pero syempre kapag hindi ko alam, tatanungin ko para doon palang parang nale-less yung worry mo na, syempre pag duty, nag-aalala na ako kung paano mo gagawin, ganoon, everything. Ayon lang din talaga kasi private bawal kami mag phone don yung isa’t isa yung parang ano namin, kahit anong pagkukwentohan na namin. Yan ang coping mechanism din bukod sa tulungan namin sa trabaho, yan ang bumubuhay samin, chismis.” (Amber)

“So kailangan mo talaga is time management, tapos pakikipag-tulungan doon sa mga kasama mong intern. Ayon huwag makikipag mataasan hangga’t maaari lagi lang down to earth” (Ruby)

“Ang ginagawa ko na lang nakikipag-anohan na lang ako sa mga tech nakikipaglokohan finefriend-friend ko na lang sila yon yung para atleast kahit papaano kahit ang bigat ng trabaho minsan parang since okay naman yung kasama ko okay na parang ine-enjoy ko na lang siya.” (Amethyst)

These participants commonly observed social support including teamwork and interpersonal relationships. Allowing peers to find strategies independently while seeking clarifications when needed was noted as an effective coping approach during their internships. Socializing with the staff and co-interns was also noted to reduce stress. A study by Dyrbye et al. (2010), as cited in Van Der Merwe et al. (2020), claimed that social support reduces the risk of stress and emotional burnout and is a significant factor in building resilience in medical students. These results complement the current observations, and it is necessary that teamwork, peer support, and positive interpersonal relationships are the factors that allow interns to cope with stress and adjust to the pressure of clinical training.

“Coping mechanism siguro parehas ha, yung ano, tulungan kami ng co-interns ko. Parang kapag may diskarte ako sa exposure, hindi nila ako pinapakialaman. Ganoon din, likewise, hindi ko rin sila pinapakialaman. Kung ganito yung strategy nila sa ganito, paano sila mag pasyente ng chest, paano kapag ang pasyente hindi makatayo, hinahayaan namin makadiskarte bawat isa. Pero syempre kapag hindi ko alam, tatanungin ko para doon palang parang nale-less yung worry mo na, syempre pag duty, nag-aalala na ako kung paano mo gagawin, ganoon, everything.” (Amber)

“Ayon huwag makikipag mataasan hangga’t maaari lagi lang down to earth then dapat willing to learn ka din lagi sa mga ituturo sayo ng mga Tech, kapag may hindi ka alam, matuto kang magsabi tapos matuto ka rin magtanong para matututo ka talaga.” (Ruby)

“Ang coping mechanism ko talaga, lagi ako nagpapaturo sa mga tech atsaka kapag nahihirapan ako sa isang bagay talagang inaaral ko siya tapos tina-try ko siya sa’kin sa sarili ko. Sa private naman kasi nga puro workloads so mas yon din nag tatanong din ako sa mga tech kung ano yung pwedeng gawin, pwedeng mga paraan or diskarte para mas mapadali yung trabaho.” (Emerald)

Self-directed learning and guidance from senior technologists were strategies employed by the participants. Interns proactively sought advice from more experienced technologists, practiced procedures independently, and reflected on their learning to overcome challenges. The participants’ responses show both autonomy and collaborative learning. This

highlights the importance of combining independent learning with mentorship to enhance practical skills and professional competence. Robinson and Persky (2020) state that self-directed learning involves students having control over their learning without relying on their teachers, setting goals, and self-isolating resources, unlike in traditional education, where teachers deliver all these elements.

“Wala lang, tiwala lang sa loob, tiwala lang sa sarili, tapos ano, dapat inspired ka sa ginagawa mo.” (Sapphire)

The participant has focused on confidence and motivation, relying on self-belief and personal inspiration to navigate clinical challenges. This indicates that interns require personal resilience and a positive mindset to manage effectively, particularly during periods of high pressure. Momeni et al. (2025) described the fact that the beliefs that students have about themselves play a crucial role in their thoughts, behavior, and motivation. The research reported that students who have more self-efficacy show confidence, high motivation and positivity to perform tasks.

“Coping mechanism wala akong masyadong maano dito kase internship eh, so you have to deal with it lang kailangan mo lang mag tiis kasi kailangan mo as a internship ganoon yon lang.” (Garnet)

Endurance and acceptance were reflected in coping strategies involving enduring difficulties and accepting challenges as part of the internship experience. This demonstrates that practicing patience and perseverance is another important strategy for handling stressful clinical situations and workloads. According to Wang (2016), as cited by Zhu et al. (2025), students with high levels of resilience are better able to regulate negative emotions, strengthen their sense of professional capacity, and maintain positive caring attitudes.

Theme 4: Professional Competence through Clinical Exposure

Clinical exposure in the hospital environment can significantly influence professionalism, technical skills, confidence, and clinical judgment. The interns' development during their clinical training was shaped by factors such as professional values, patient communication skills, and radiation safety principles. These findings reinforce the overarching theme of Professional Competence through Clinical Exposure.

“Professionalism talaga, yon din tinuro samin. Pinapili kasi kami ano mahalaga, attitude or professionalism. Most of us sinagot namin, attitude pero mali pala kami. Sabi ni Sir I, head yon ng public, professionalism ang mahalaga” (Amber)

This participant pointed out that the hospital environment in general may contribute to the development of their professional values. This corresponds to the study by Schweitzer and Sarkany (2020), who noted that one of the most important criteria that can determine how radiologic technology interns can get more professional and gain experience is in hospital settings.

“Sa public, doon talaga marami akong natutunan. Tulad ng pag-ano, sa mga machine, sa pag-handle ng mga pasyente, at nasanay ako sa toxic na hospital.” (Sapphire)

“Sa private kasi tulad nga ng sinasabi ko mas onti yung cases don, kasi pag ako nag x-ray ako pag hindi kaya ng pasyente syempre na-ano ako ipagawa parang nag aalangan ako ipagawa pero ang tinuro sakin ng mga tech ko doon na bawal, kailangan kahit hindi kaya kailangan pilitin ganoon parang dun ita-try pero sa public talagang hindi mo kailangan mag tanong sa tech kasi kailangan ikaw ang gagawa ng paraan, so nung nasa private ako siguro naka kuha ako ng mga skills sa pagpo posisyon, sa factor pero ngayon sa public mas nahasa siya kasi sa public hindi ka talaga tutulongan ng tech, ikaw lang talaga.”(Emerald)

“Sa private yung previous ko ano meron silang may time n laging nagtatanong sila so dun sa mga pagtatanong nila may mga natututunan ako hindi katulad sa private na work work lang talaga since ang dami talagang pasyente ng public ang daming pasyente tapos iba-iba pa.” (Amethyst)

These participants had stated that they had improved their technical abilities through experiential learning, a toxic environment, case variability, and inquiry. These findings are supported by Almadani et al. (2024) Hospitals with a consistent flow of mixed cases provided interns with an opportunity to reapply their technical skills and clinical reasoning.

“Parehas lang naman, natutunan ko is yung tamang positioning sa patient tapos yung tamang pakikipag-usap so dapat lagi tayong merong pakikipag kapwa tao. Tapos, yon lang yung maayos na pakikipag usap sa pasyente.” (Ruby)

This participant explained that both settings have gained knowledge and enhanced patient communication skills during imaging procedures, strengthened appropriate patient placement, and reinforced radiation safety principles. This perspective aligns with existing literature emphasizing the critical role of communication in radiography. As Nghipukuula et al. (2021) mentioned, effective communication during radiographic procedures has a wide range of advantages: it improves the patient's understanding of the treatment plan and enhances the patient adherence to the treatment plan as well as radiographers', human-to-human communication: Radiographers are the initial contact with patients, and sound communication abilities enable them to protect the patient more effectively and establish an effective interaction.

Theme 5: Bridging Theory to Clinical Reality through Varied Internship Experiences

Bridging Theory to clinical reality through diverse hospital environments enables interns to adapt to varying circumstances and develop essential skills. Different variations in workflow, procedures, patient volume, and learning experiences influence how interns enhance and solidify their competence.

"Magkaiba ang by theory atsaka sa clinical practice iba-iba din ang body habitus, iba-iba din ang lagay ng pasyente. So ikaw matututo kang dumiskarte. Siguro nandon yung book or yung theory as guide, pero in real life matututo kang dumiskarte na makuha yung anatomy ng maayos.." (Amber)

"Sobrang laking tulong nung internship program kasi naa-apply natin yung theoretical sa actual." (Ruby)

Both participants emphasized the importance of applying theory to practice through exposure to private and public hospital settings. It pointed out that theory acts as a guide, and real clinical situations enable them to find ways in which they can handle the situation. This supports the study of Shafuda et al. (2025), who discussed that clinical training aids interns in implementing the theoretical information into the actual clinical setting, enabling them to gain competence and confidence.

"Napakahalaga non kasi makikita mo yung difference ng ospital na private tsaka public. Sa public, madami ang pasyente tapos sa private, kaunti. Mas mae-enhance yung skills mo sa profession kasi maraming pasyente, mas madami kang ma-hahandle." (Sapphire)

"Important siya kasi na-experience mo yung public and private na setting ng hospital. Marami kang matututunan. Sa public, maraming pasyente kaya mae-experience mo yung handling." (Amethyst)

"Importante talaga na mag-rotation ka sa isang public tsaka sa isang private. Magkaiba kasi yung environment ng public tsaka ng private. Sa private, marami kang matututunan in terms of workloads at sa mga gawaing pang-RadTech sa loob ng hospital. Sa public, doon mo mas mahahasa yung skills mo sa pagha-handle ng pasyente." (Emerald)

Participants' responses emphasized the importance of internships between private and public hospitals in developing clinical competencies. It is mentioned that exposure to public hospitals enabled them to handle more patients, thereby enhancing their skills and confidence. Private hospitals provided opportunities for workflow in a more controlled environment. The participant was able to develop their clinical skills and gain a better understanding of their professional responsibilities. A similar study by Pasay-an et al. (2025) highlighted that despite the inherent stresses and heavy workload, the interns themselves viewed their internship as a helpful learning experience that helped them grow and become ready to enter professional practice, stimulated them to stay active and motivated even when they had a difficult day, and enabled them to see the value of perseverance and reflection on what they learned.

"Importante na maranasan mo yung private kasi don ka talaga matututo ng strict way at proper way. Sa public naman, matututunan mo yung positioning kahit na super sugatan na siya, may fractures na siya. Makakagawa ka ng ways na maipakita yung structures na kailangan kahit ganun yung pasyente." (Garnet)

However, this statement shows the importance of internships in public and private hospitals for learning structured practices, developing problem-solving skills, and gaining diverse clinical experience. The participant stated that in the case of private hospitals, they taught them the correct, stricter way to execute procedures, whereas in public hospitals, they helped them develop their positioning skills and adapt to different situations where patients have serious injuries. Research by Fernández-Regueras et al. (2023) has found that effective clinical exposure and supervision significantly improve students' confidence and competence.

Themes 6: Enhancing Internship Quality through Preparation and Support

Internship quality depends on appropriate training and support to produce capable and work-ready graduates. This includes the importance of cultivating a positive mindset, the necessity for facility improvements, the need for stricter supervision, the promotion of active learning practices, increased mental health awareness, and the establishment of

discipline. In both public and private hospital environments, these factors collectively influence how interns adapt, perform, and grow professionally throughout their clinical training.

"Private or public ito yung ano namin kumbaga mantra namin. Enjoy lang. Promise. Kahit tamad na tamad ka, pumasok ka. Kahit nga may sakit ka, pumasok ka. I-enjoy mo lang. Cherish bawat moment." (Amber)

"Tapos alagaan niyo rin yung mental health niyo kasi iba rin yung effect nung internship sa mental health." (Emerald)

"Mag-aral, mag-aral ng positioning, tapos uminom ng maraming vitamins. Kailangan kasi matatag yung loob mo eh kapag nasa, ano tawag doon, nasa field ka talaga." (Sapphire)

Participants emphasized that a positive mindset, enjoyment and mental health awareness is essential in the clinical experiences of radiologic technology interns. It demonstrates that a positive attitude allows interns to cope with stress, stay focused, and maintain their performance. Ultimately, developing a positive attitude will help one become more resilient and grow professionally during clinical training. In line with this observation, Pasay-an et al. (2025) revealed that even with stress and workloads, interns regarded clinical internship as a valuable learning experience that enhanced resilience, motivation, and preparedness to practice professionally. Similarly, a study by Balay-Odao et al. (2024) demonstrates that proactive mental health maintenance during the internship is necessary because of its role in sustaining performance over time, managing stress, and enabling the full range of clinical learning.

"Tapos, hangga't maaari din sana kung kaya ng budget, i-upgrade yung CR to DR para maging madali yung workload kasi sobrang dami talagang pasyente kapag sa public." (Ruby)

"Suggestion ko sa public ako siguro like ayusin talaga yung facility and kumpletuhin yung modalities kasi yun yung kailangan talaga sa public eh." (Garnet)

The need for facility improvement and complete modalities was emphasized by the participants, particularly in public hospitals. This implies that outdated or limited equipment may contribute to increased workload and operational challenges during clinical training. This supports the study of Nigatu et al. (2023), who discussed the problems in medical imaging services in the public hospitals. The research results revealed that machine failures, slow maintenance, poor facilities, and a lack of personnel were some of the factors that slowed service delivery. Such problems led to delays in diagnosis and treatment, increased waiting time of patients, and missed the opportunity to use the external facilities, which can provide an understanding of the necessity to improve the facilities and equip them with new technologies to facilitate the work process, improve the quality of services, and provide new clinical training.

"Siguro mare-recommend ko, kapag sa public hospital, dapat mas maayos yung supervision nila, mas mahigpit para mas maging maganda talaga yung workload, yung ethics." (Ruby)

However, this participant stated the necessity of stricter supervision, especially in public hospitals. Stricter supervision was seen as helpful in developing discipline, accountability, and overall efficiency throughout clinical training, even though the current supervision was seen as appropriate. This corresponds to the study by O' Connor and McNulty (2024), which states that clinical learning environments affect the quality of experience and development among learners. It proved that the variation in clinical exposure, supervision, and professional expectations between the public and the private hospital could impact the learning outcome of the intern, to justify the observation that a participant made regarding the fact that stricter supervision was observed in the private hospital.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concluded that the performance and professional development of radiologic technology interns are shaped not by a single clinical environment, but by the complementary learning experiences offered by both public and private hospitals. Each setting contributes distinct yet equally important aspects that collectively enhance the interns' competencies. The findings indicate that workload plays a critical role in the development of clinical skills. The high patient volume in public hospitals, although physically demanding and at times stressful, fosters greater hands-on experience, particularly in managing trauma and complex cases. This environment strengthens technical proficiency, adaptability, and decision-making under pressure. In contrast, the lighter workload in private hospitals creates a less stressful environment, allowing interns to focus more on accuracy and efficiency, though it may limit their exposure to a wide range of critical cases. The study suggests that the effectiveness of supervision is largely influenced by the radiologic technologist, rather than solely by the institution. The way technologists engage with and mentor interns significantly contributes to interns' confidence, independence, and overall learning experience.

The study further concludes that while learning opportunities vary across institutions, each holds significant value. Public hospitals offer broader exposure to a wide range of diverse and complex cases, which enhances critical thinking and

practical skills. In contrast, private hospitals provide access to advanced imaging technologies and modern equipment, fostering technological proficiency. These distinctions emphasize that comprehensive professional development necessitates both extensive clinical exposure and familiarity with advanced practices.

To improve clinical training, educational institutions should strengthen partnerships with affiliated hospitals to ensure structured rotations and balanced clinical exposure. While these results are significant, the study has limitations as it is based on self-reported information subject to bias and a single internship period where no performance changes over time were recorded. These offer opportunities for refinement in future studies by incorporating a broader range of hospitals and participants to account for differences in hospital policies and workload. Future research should investigate additional factors influencing performance such as hospital resources, workflow efficiency, and organizational culture to offer a more comprehensive understanding and better prepare students for real-world clinical practice.

Acknowledgements

The researchers would like to express their sincere gratitude and appreciation to all individuals who extended their support, guidance, and assistance in the completion of this research paper. Their contributions, encouragement, and valuable insights greatly helped the researchers throughout the process of conducting and accomplishing this study.

To Mrs. Catherine Joy A. Dominguez RRT, MSRT(c), our research professor, for sharing her knowledge and providing guidance that helped improve our research.

To Ms. Samantha Kim A. De Vera, RPh, RGC, our research adviser, for her unwavering guidance and mentorship throughout the completion of this study.

To the panel members: Mr. Juan Guiller V. Santero, RRT, MD, Chairman of the Panel; Mr. Daniel Aaron D. Manankil, RRT, RSO, MS CPD; and Mr. Dennis M. Prescilla, LPT, MAEd, for their valuable advice, ideas, and corrections that contributed to the improvement of this study.

To Ms. Mary Joyce P. Colitoy, LPT, our grammarian, for the effort of checking and editing this study.

To Mrs. Manuella M. Ganaden, MBA, our research analyst, for dedicating her significant time and expertise to analyzing and validating the results.

To the Senior Radiologic Technology Interns who participated in this research study. Without their cooperation, this research would not have been possible.

Funding

This research was funded by the researchers. This research received no external funding from any public, commercial, or not-for-profit funding agency, and no organization provided financial support for the conduct of the study, authorship, or publication of this article.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

References

Aguilar, P., Baliber, M. T., Javier, R. M., Anne, N., Christian, R., & Mendoza, K. E. (2023). Problems encountered during clinical internship by the radiologic technology interns of De La Salle Medical and Health Sciences Institute. *GreenPrints*. <https://greenprints.dlshsi.edu.ph/bsrt/679>

- Alhazmi, A. A., & Kaufmann, A. (2022). Phenomenological qualitative methods applied to the analysis of cross-cultural experience in novel educational social contexts. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 785134. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.785134>
- Almadani, N., Hables, R. M., Alharbi, J., Alamri, M., & Alshammari, M. (2024). Nurse interns' perception of clinical preparation and readiness for clinical internship experiences. *Journal of Nursing Management*, 2024, 6682600. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2024/6682600>
- Alumran, A., Almutawa, H., Alzain, Z., Althumairi, A., & Khalid, N. (2020). Comparing public and private hospitals' service quality. *Journal of Public Health (Berlin)*, 29(4), 839–845. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10389-019-01188-9>
- Balay-Odao, E. M., Moulic, A. A., & Paloga, C. N. (2024). "Influence of Perceived Clinical Supervision of Student Nurses on their Burnout Experience". *Health Professions Education*: Vol. 10: Iss. 1, Article 4. <https://doi.org/10.55890/2452-3011.1061>
- Begum, F., Said, J., Hossain, S. Z., & Ali, M. A. (2022). Patient satisfaction level and its determinants after admission in public and private tertiary care hospitals in Bangladesh. *Frontiers in Health Services*, 2, 952221. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frhs.2022.952221>
- Chinene, B., Sanyamandwe, C., & Hlahla, T. (2023). Challenges experienced by radiography students during clinical placements in a low-resource setting: A Qualitative phenomenological study. *South African Radiographer*, 61(2), 32–40. <https://doi.org/10.54450/saradio.2023.61.2.753>
- Colina, T. C. (2023). Dental student perceptions on clinic supervision: A qualitative study. *Journal of Advances in Dental Practice and Research*, 2, 24–27. https://doi.org/10.25259/jadpr_3_2023
- Cudjoe, E. (2023). Making sense of Husserlian phenomenological philosophy in empirical research. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 22, 16094069231171099. <https://doi.org/10.1177/16094069231171099>
- Fernández, R. A., García López, E., & Martínez Pérez, R. (2023). Clinical supervision and competence development among radiography students. *Radiography*, 29(3), 550–556. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radi.2023.02.012>
- Mishra, D. (2024). Patient satisfaction and experience with radiology services in public and private hospitals. *World Journal of Biology Pharmacy and Health Sciences*, 20(3), 323–338. <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjbpsh.2024.20.3.1032>
- Momeni, M., Asadi, M., Shadin, H., Noorian, S., & Senmar, M. (2025). Self-efficacy of clinical performance in nursing students and its relationship with the motivation of field choice and clinical education status. *BMC Medical Education*, 25(1), 767. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-025-07372-8>
- Nair, S. S., Thomas, K. A., & Prem, S. S. (2021). "The Organizational Pedestal of Quality of Care Climate in Health Care Excellence." *Zeitschrift Für Evidenz, Fortbildung Und Qualität Im Gesundheitswesen*, 160, 34–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.zefq.2020.09.006>
- National Privacy Commission. (2012). Republic Act 10173 - Data Privacy Act of 2012. National Privacy Commission. <https://privacy.gov.ph/data-privacy-act>
- Nghipukuula, J. S. N., Daniels, E. R., & Karera, A. (2021). Effectiveness of communication between student radiographers and patients before, during and after radiographic procedures. *South African Radiographer*, 59(2), 7–14. <https://doi.org/10.54450/saradio.2021.59.2.587>
- Nigatu, A. M., Yilma, T. M., Gezie, L. D., Gebrewold, Y., Gullslett, M. K., Mengiste, S. A., & Tilahun, B. (2023). Medical imaging consultation practices and challenges at public hospitals. *BMC Health Services Research*, 23(1), 787. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-023-09652-9>
- Nuruzzaman, M., Zapata, T., De Oliveira Cruz, V., Alam, S., Tune, S. N. B. K., & Joarder, T. (2022). Adopting workload-based staffing norms at public sector health facilities in Bangladesh. *Human Resources for Health*, 19(S1), 151. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12960-021-00697-7>
- O'Connor, M., & McNulty, J. (2024). Radiography students' viewpoints of the clinical learning environment: A cross-sectional study. *Radiography*, 30(1), 367–374. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radi.2023.12.005>
- Oluka, A. (2025). Phenomenological Research Strategy: Descriptive and Interpretive Approaches. *F1000Research*, 14, 725–725. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.166273.1>
- Pasay-An, E., Alsharani, S. R., Shanmugam, S. R., Alalawi, R. H., Alreshidi, M. S., Alrashidi, N. A., Gonzales, A., Gutierrez, J., Areola, B., Gonzales, F., & Dominguez, A. J. (2025). Exploring nursing intern students' experiences of stress and resilience during internship using photovoice. *BMC Nursing*, 24(1), 1037. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-025-03701-w>
- Pichay, A., Peña, A. B., Pisueña, J. L., Peña, S., Piano, E. E., & Delos Santos, N. (2025). The perception of adults in Manila about the accessibility, availability and affordability of private and public healthcare services for neurological emergencies. *Journal of Medicine, UST*, 9(S1). <https://doi.org/10.35460/2546-1621.2025-0078>
- Robinson, J., & Persky, A. (2020). Developing self-directed learners. *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education*, 84(3). <https://doi.org/10.5688/ajpe847512>
- Schweitzer, A. D., & Sarkany, D. (2020). The importance of the clinical internship for the radiologist. *Academic Radiology*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acra.2020.05.028>
- Shafuda, S., Daniels, E., & Karera, A. (2024). Bridging theory and practice: Experiences of diagnostic radiography students during clinical training in resource-constrained settings. *Journal of Medical Radiation Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmrs.85>

- Tamayo, R. L. J., Quintin-Gutierrez, M. K. F., Campo, M. B., Lim, M. J. F., & Labuni, P. T. (2022). Rationing of nursing care and its relationship to nurse practice environment in a tertiary public hospital. *Acta Medica Philippina*, 56(3), 64–71. <https://doi.org/10.47895/amp.vi0.3124>
- Van Der Merwe, L. J., Botha, A., & Joubert, G. (2020). Resilience and coping strategies of undergraduate medical students at the University of the Free State. *South African Journal of Psychiatry*, 26, 1471. <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajpsychiatry.v26i0.1471>
- Zhu, W., Jiao, T., & Chen, G. (2025). The impact of clinical learning environment factors on caring behaviors: the mediating role of psychological resilience among nursing intern students. *BMC Nursing*, 24(1), 1187. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-025-03840-0>

Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.